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Impact of Single Parenthood on Academic Adjustment of Basic School Students in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the impact of single parenthood on academic adjustment of basic school students in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. Four research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of all basic school teachers in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State which is 5,874. The sample size of the study was 400 secondary school teachers. The sample size was arrived at using the Taro Yamane formula for finding sample size of a population. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled “Single Parenthood and Academic Adjustment Questionnaire (SPAAQ).” The questionnaire was made up of 20 items and followed the Likert modified four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The options had numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. To establish the reliability of the instrument, a trial test was conducted with 40 students. The scores from the trial were analysed using the Cronbach's Alpha correlation coefficient, which produced a reliability coefficient of 0.77. The data were analysed based on the research questions using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (X^2) goodness of fit test at .05 level of significance, with 2.50 serving as the criterion mean for decision making on the items to be responded to and below 2.50 was considered negative and disagree. The findings of the study were as follows; single parenthood has significant impact on school attendance of basic school students in Makurdi Local Government; single parenthood has significant impact on class participation of basic school students; single parenthood has significant impact on extracurricular activities of basic school students and single parenthood has significant impact on study habits of basic school students. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made among others; implement flexible scheduling and support programs. Schools could offer early morning or late afternoon tutoring sessions to accommodate students who may have responsibilities at home. Also, foster an inclusive and supportive classroom environment.

Keywords: Single Parenthood, Academic Adjustment, Class Attendance, Class Participation, Extracurricular Activities and Study Habits.

INTRODUCTION

When students are enrolled into schools, this is done with the hope that they adjust academically, socially, psychologically and emotionally so that they can perform to their highest potentials. However, a myriad of influences impact on how the students adjust and the performance they put up. A common example of such influences is the family of the learner. There are different family types including single parent families.

Single parent family is a family with children headed by a parent who is widowed or divorced and not remarried or by parent who has never married. Single parenting is therefore a situation where only a parent, either the father or mother is saddled with the responsibility of taking care of the child (Adegboyega, 2019). A single parent is a parent, not living with spouse or partner, who has most of the day-to-day responsibilities in raising the children (Munir, Rani, Ali & Afzal, 2021). Raising a child or children by one parent, either the mother or father alone, for most of the time is reported to be quite challenging, placing extraordinary demands on both the parent and the children. Single parents may have profound negative impact on student's academic performance as parents play an important role in most children's academic development. Previous research indicates that children from both parents perform better than children from single parents. This was attributed to the limited time a single parent has to spend on their child's academic work. The resultant effect of this would be an impact on the child's academic adjustment.

Academic adjustment is a broad concept that encompasses both academic achievement and attainment and other important variables like school attendance, class participation, study habit, use of library, participation in extracurricular activities among others. Attendance has been defined as the physical presence of the students in schools/classes. Attendance at schools is not merely being bodily present but including actual participation in the work and activities of the school. Fagbenle (2008) identified two types of attendance as regular attendance and irregular attendance. According to the author, regular attendance is characterized as being present, punctual and being involved in the activities of the school while irregular is a deliberate absenteeism of oneself from school for no just cause. As per school policy, the attendance of students affects their grades. Sometimes, students' absenteeism from school has various reasons. Some of these reasons can be a bad company, personal issues, health issues, and family problems. Single parenthood can have various effects on a child's school attendance, but it is important to note that every situation is unique, and individual circumstances can greatly influence outcomes. However, single parents often shoulder the financial responsibility alone, which can lead to increased stress and potentially limit their ability to provide resources for their children. This may affect school attendance if, for example, they cannot afford transportation or extracurricular activities that could enhance their child's educational experience (Ferrell, 2009; Mrinde, 2014).

Participation in class is a combination of coming to class and paying attention once there. Class participation has been found to be positively correlated with academic adjustment (Landin & Perez, 2015). Class participation involves two variables of attending and the act of sharing in the activities of the class or other teacher-led activities. Single parenthood can potentially impact a child's class participation in various ways, but it is important to note that the effects can vary widely depending on individual circumstances, the quality of parenting, and the support systems in place. Single parents may have additional responsibilities and less time to dedicate to their children due to managing household chores, work, and other commitments. This could potentially limit the amount of time available for helping with homework, engaging in extracurricular activities, or simply having conversations about school. As a result, a child might be less prepared or motivated to actively participate in class (Ansah, 2017). Additionally, single parents may face more stress and emotional strain compared to those in two-parent households. This could potentially affect their ability to provide consistent emotional support and encouragement, which are crucial for a child's confidence and willingness to participate in class (Mabuza and Okeke, 2014).

Study habits refer to the techniques, and practices that individuals use to enhance their learning and academic performance. Study habits is how one studies. That is, the habits which students form during

their school years (Ebele & Olofu, 2017). According to Nneji (2002), study habits are those learning tendencies that enable students to work privately. Study habit, when broken down involves the time put into study, method used in studying and content of study. Children often look to their parents as role models. In single-parent households, the parent's own approach to education and learning can have a significant impact on the child's study habits. If the parent values education and demonstrates this through their own behaviour, it can positively influence the child. Furthermore, parental involvement, such as helping with homework, attending parent-teacher meetings, and providing a structured study environment, can have a positive effect on a child's study habits. However, in single-parent households, there might be fewer available resources for this kind of involvement. And there might be negative impact on the child's academic adjustment (Falana and Ayodele, 2012).

Extracurricular activities refer to any organized, non-academic activities that students participate in outside of their regular school curriculum. These activities can take place in school or in the community and cover a wide range of interests and pursuits. Bartkus, Nemelka, Nemelka and Gardener (2012) define extracurricular activities as academic or non-academic activities that are conducted under the auspices of the school but occur outside of normal classroom time and are not part of the curriculum. The authors maintain that extracurricular activities do not involve a grade or academic credit and participation is optional on the part of the student. Participating in extracurricular activities can have numerous benefits for students, including personal development, skill-building, socialization, and college or job applications (Farb & Matjasko, 2012). Single parenthood can potentially influence a child's participation in extracurricular activities, but it is important to note that the impact can vary widely depending on numerous certain factors. Firstly, single parents often have to juggle multiple responsibilities, including work, household chores, and childcare. This may limit the time available for transporting children to and from extracurricular activities, supervising practices, or attending events. Secondly, single-parent households may face financial challenges that can affect a child's ability to participate in costly extracurricular activities. Some activities require fees for equipment, uniforms, lessons, or travel expenses, which might be more difficult for single parents to afford.

Statement of the Problem

The school is a miniature society and through teaching prepares students for the larger society. To a large extent, how a student performs within the school environment can significantly influence the opportunities available to them in the society. A student's adjustment to school and the teaching-learning process is key to their optimum performance in the various aspects of the curriculum that are exposed to them including extracurricular activities. The researchers have observed that there might be significant differences between the adjustment levels of students from single parenthood and those from families with both parents. This was attributed to the fact that the circumstances surrounding the upbringing of both groups of students are different. For example, a look at the socioeconomic capabilities of an average single parent in Makurdi as compared to an average couple would reveal that the couple would possess more in terms of resources, finances and emotional and psychological stability. However, this might be the direct opposite in certain cases. But in the current study the researchers aim to find out the impact of single parenthood on the academic adjustment of Basic School students in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered to guide the study:

1. What is the impact of single parenthood on school attendance of basic school students in Makurdi Local Government?
2. What is the impact of single parenthood on class participation of basic school students?
3. What is the impact of single parenthood on extracurricular activities of basic school students?
4. What is the impact of single parenthood on study habits of basic school students?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Single parenthood has no significant impact on school attendance of basic school students in Makurdi Local Government.
2. Single parenthood has no significant impact on class participation of basic school students.
3. Single parenthood has no significant impact on extracurricular activities of basic school students.
4. Single parenthood has no significant impact on study habits of basic school students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of all basic school teachers in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State which is 5,874. The sample size of the study was 400 secondary school teachers. The sample size was arrived at using the Taro Yamane formula for finding sample size of a population. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled “Single Parenthood and Academic Adjustment Questionnaire (SPAAQ).” The questionnaire was made up of 20 items and followed the Likert modified four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The options had numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. The data were analysed based on the research questions using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (X^2) goodness of fit test at .05 level of significance, with 2.50 serving as the criterion mean for decision making on the items to be responded to and below 2.50 was considered negative and disagree.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Research Question 1

What is the impact of single parenthood on school attendance of basic school students in Makurdi Local Government?

Table 1: Analysis of Impact of Single Parenthood on School Attendance of Basic School Students in Makurdi Local Government.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision	
1	Students from single-parent households are more prone to absenteeism.	46	189	76	89	2.48	.96	Rejected	
2	Work-family balance can hinder single parents' ability to ensure regular school attendance for their children.	117	194	33	56	2.93	.97	Accepted	
3	Limited finances can restrict transportation access, affecting school attendance for students from single-parent households.	60	243	62	35	2.82	.79	Accepted	
4	Late arrival to school is common among students from single-parent households.	49	222	73	56	2.66	.87	Accepted	
5	Irregular attendance is common among pupils from single-parent households.	51	184	95	70	2.54	.93	Accepted	
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		$\bar{X}= 2.68$					SD= .902		Accepted

Table 1 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents’ responses for items 1 to 5 are 2.48, 2.93, 2.82, 2.66, and 2.54 with corresponding standard deviations of .96, .97, .79, .87, and .93 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 2.68 with the cluster standard deviation of .902 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that single parenthood has impact on school attendance of basic school students in Makurdi Local Government.

Research Question 2

What is the impact of single parenthood on class participation of basic school students?

Table 2: Analysis of Impact of Single Parenthood on Class Participation of Basic School Students in Makurdi Local Government.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	Limited finances in single-parent households can affect students' access to learning materials, impacting class participation.	275	90	35	0	3.60	.65	Accepted
7	Pupils from single-parent households may face challenges, potentially impacting their class participation.	62	245	58	35	2.83	.79	Accepted
8	Pupils from single-parent households may show behaviours affecting class participation.	53	129	107	111	2.31	1.018	Rejected
9	Pupils from single-parent households typically display positive classroom behaviour.	51	279	56	14	2.92	.63	Accepted
10	Some pupils from single parent households display disruptive classroom behaviour.	56	203	71	70	2.61	.93	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 2.85$ SD= .8038								Accepted

Table 2 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10 are 3.60, 2.83, 2.31, 2.92, and 2.61 with corresponding standard deviations of .65, .79, 1.018, .63, and .93 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 2.85 with the cluster standard deviation of .80 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that single parenthood has impact on class participation of basic school students.

Research Question 3

What is the impact of single parenthood on extracurricular activities of basic school students?

Table 3: Analysis of Impact of Single Parenthood on Extracurricular Activities of Basic School Students in Makurdi Local Government.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	Limited finances in single-parent homes affect students' access to extracurricular activities.	117	188	12	83	2.85	1.064	Accepted
12	Financial constraints in single-parent households may impact students' ability to engage in extracurricular activities.	92	223	12	73	2.84	.982	Accepted
13	Pupils from single-parent households do not always participate in fee-based extracurricular activities.	123	184	29	64	2.92	1.008	Accepted
14	Attending field trips poses challenges for students from single-parent households.	58	232	36	74	2.69	.937	Accepted
15	Pupils single-parent homes do not fully participate in extracurricular activities.	135	162	15	88	2.86	1.113	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 2.83$ SD= 1.02								Accepted

Table 3 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 11 to 15 are 2.85, 2.84, 2.92, 2.69, and 2.86 with corresponding standard deviations of 1.008, .910, 1.039, .918, and 1.115 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 2.83 with the cluster standard deviation of 1.02 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that single parenthood has impact on extracurricular activities of basic school students.

Research Question 4

What is the impact of single parenthood on study habits of basic school students?

Table 4: Analysis of Impact of Single Parenthood on Study Habits of Basic School Students in Makurdi Local Government.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
16	Financial constraints in single-parent homes affect the availability of educational materials for children.	120	160	80	40	2.90	.95	Accepted
17	Single parents are not actively participating in assisting their child with homework.	320	60	20	0	3.75	.54	Accepted
18	Work-family balance decreases parental involvement in assisting students with school assignments.	160	180	40	20	3.20	.81	Accepted
19	Limited finances in single-parent homes affect students' access to learning materials impacting their study habits.	183	139	42	36	3.17	.95	Accepted
20	Students from single-parent homes may encounter difficulties accessing essential learning resources.	170	172	1	57	3.14	.99	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.23$ SD= .85								Accepted

Table 4 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 16 to 20 are 2.90, 3.75, 3.20, 3.17, and 3.14 with corresponding standard deviations of .95, .53, .81, .95, and .99 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.23 with the cluster standard deviation of .85 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that single parenthood has impact on study habits of basic school students.

Hypotheses Testing

In testing the hypotheses of this study, Chi-square (X^2) was used to test the responses of respondents at .05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Single parenthood has no significant impact on school attendance of basic school students in Makurdi Local Government.

Table 5: Chi-square Test of Impact of Single Parenthood on School Attendance of Basic School Students in Makurdi Local Government.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X^2_{cal}	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	115.340	.000	Sig.
SA	46	100.0					
A	189	100.0					
D	76	100.0					
SD	89	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 5 revealed that $\chi^2 = 115.340$, $df=3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that single parenthood has no significant impact on school attendance of basic school students in Makurdi Local Government is

therefore, rejected. This implies that single parenthood has significant impact on school attendance of basic school students in Makurdi Local Government.

Hypothesis 2

Single parenthood has no significant impact on class participation of basic school students.

Table 6: Chi-square Test of Impact of Single Parenthood on Class Participation of Basic School Students in Makurdi Local Government.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	32.200	.000	Sig.
SA	53	100.0					
A	129	100.0					A
D	107	100.0					
SD	111	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 6 revealed that $\chi^2 = 32.200$, $df=3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that single parenthood has no significant impact on class participation of basic school students is therefore, not accepted. This implies that single parenthood has significant impact on class participation of basic school students.

Hypothesis 3

Single parenthood has no significant impact on extracurricular activities of basic school students.

Table 7: Chi-square Test of Impact of Single Parenthood on Extracurricular Activities of Basic School Students in Makurdi Local Government.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	124.380	.000	Sig.
SA	135	100.0					
A	162	100.0					
D	15	100.0					
SD	88	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 7 revealed that $\chi^2 = 124.380$, $df=3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that single parenthood has no significant impact on extracurricular activities of basic school students is therefore, rejected. This implies that single parenthood has significant impact on extracurricular activities of basic school students.

Hypothesis 4

Single parenthood has no significant impact on study habits of basic school students.

Table 8: Chi-square Test of Impact of Single Parenthood on Study Habits of Basic School Students in Makurdi Local Government.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	80.000	.000	Sig.
SA	120	100.0					
A	160	100.0					
D	80	100.0					
SD	40	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 8 revealed that $\chi^2 = 80.000$, $df=3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that single parenthood has no significant impact on study habits of basic school students is therefore, rejected. This implies that single parenthood has significant impact on study habits of basic school students.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this research was organized around the research questions and hypotheses. The four null hypotheses that were postulated and tested were all rejected.

The first finding of the study revealed that single parenthood has significant impact on school attendance of basic school students in Makurdi Local Government. The study's findings indicate that single parenthood significantly impacts the school attendance of basic school students. Single parents often face numerous challenges, such as balancing work and childcare responsibilities, which can lead to inconsistencies in their children's school attendance. This finding is similar that of Amadi (2019), who found in a study that, single parenting had significant impact on the school attendance of students from single parent homes. This finding was also supported by Olubiyi, Ibraheem, Okesina, Onifade, Okesina and Malomo (2019). They noted that, these parents might struggle with limited time, financial constraints, and lack of support, making it difficult to ensure regular and timely school attendance for their children. Moreover, students from single-parent households may need to take on additional responsibilities at home, such as caring for younger siblings or managing household chores, further contributing to irregular attendance. The absence of a second parent to share these duties often exacerbates the situation, leading to increased absenteeism and potential academic setbacks for the students involved.

The second finding of the study revealed that single parenthood has significant impact on class participation of basic school students. Students from single-parent households may experience heightened stress and emotional strain due to the unique challenges their families face, such as economic hardship, lack of parental support, and time constraints. These factors can lead to reduced focus and engagement in the classroom. This finding corroborates with that of Amadi (2019), the author avers that without consistent encouragement and assistance with schoolwork, children may feel less confident in participating in class discussions and activities. Munir, Rani, Ali and Afzal (2021), also revealed the same results from their study. Additionally, single parents may have less time to be involved in their child's education, including attending school events or meeting with teachers, which can further hinder a child's motivation and ability to actively engage in class. The absence of a supportive and stable home environment may contribute to feelings of isolation or disengagement, ultimately affecting their overall academic performance and participation.

The third finding of the study revealed that single parenthood has significant impact on extracurricular activities of basic school students. The study highlights that single parenthood significantly impacts the participation of basic school students in extracurricular activities. Children from single-parent households often face constraints that limit their ability to engage in activities beyond the classroom. Financial limitations can make it difficult for single parents to afford fees, equipment, or transportation associated with extracurricular programs. Additionally, single parents, who may be juggling multiple jobs or extensive work hours, often have less time to transport their children to and from activities or to attend events. This lack of logistical support and parental involvement can discourage children from participating. This finding is similar to that of Olubiyi, Ibraheem, Okesina, Onifade, Okesina and Malomo (2019), and Sackey, Mensah and Obeng (2020), who noted that single parenthood affected the participation of students in school activities. Furthermore, the increased responsibilities at home, such as caring for siblings or handling household chores, can leave students with less time and energy for extracurricular pursuits. As a result, these students miss out on the social, physical, and cognitive benefits that such activities provide, potentially affecting their overall development and well-being.

The fourth finding of the study revealed that single parenthood has significant impact on study habits of basic school students. The study reveals that single parenthood significantly impacts the study habits of basic school students. In single-parent households, the lone parent often faces immense pressures to balance work, household duties, and parenting responsibilities, which can limit the time and energy they have to supervise and support their children's academic activities. This lack of supervision and guidance can lead to the development of poor study habits, as children may not receive the necessary structure and encouragement to complete their homework or prepare for exams effectively. This finding is similar to that of Oyediran (2019), who noted that single parenthood affected the study habits and academic

performance of students from single parent homes. This was also supported by Ntumi, Larbi and Yirenkyi (2016). Additionally, single parents may lack the resources to provide a conducive study environment, such as a quiet space or necessary educational materials. Children might also take on additional responsibilities at home, further detracting from the time available for studying. Consequently, these students may struggle with organization, time management, and maintaining a consistent study routine, adversely affecting their academic performance and long-term educational outcomes.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It was concluded that single parenthood has impact on academic adjustment of basic school students in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Implement flexible scheduling and support programs. Schools could offer early morning or late afternoon tutoring sessions to accommodate students who may have responsibilities at home. Additionally, schools could provide resources such as transportation assistance and attendance incentives to encourage regular attendance.
2. Foster an inclusive and supportive classroom environment. Teachers should be trained to recognize and address the unique challenges faced by students from single-parent households. Encouraging active participation through group work, interactive lessons, and providing additional support where needed can help improve engagement.
3. Increase accessibility to extracurricular activities. Schools should offer a variety of extracurricular activities at different times to accommodate varying schedules. Providing scholarships or financial assistance for activity fees and supplies, and ensuring safe and reliable transportation to and from activities can help increase participation.
4. Provide targeted academic support and resources. Schools can establish homework clubs, study groups, and after-school programs that provide a structured environment for completing assignments. Additionally, offering workshops on effective study techniques and providing access to resources such as libraries and online learning tools can support the development of good study habits.

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